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Perspectives in Grammar Descriptions of Sign Languages

Overview

- ❖ Research questions and methodology
- ❖ Comments on contemporary practices
- ❖ Emerging practices: Estonia
- ❖ Summary

Rationale

- ? Format of grammar description of sign languages
- ? Reliability, reproducibility, sustainability, usability and user-friendliness of grammar descriptions
- ? Overview of theories and methodological approaches

Two Main Research Questions

What is the grammar description concerning sign languages?

What practices are there in the development of grammar descriptions in sign languages?

Research methodology I: Data collection

- ❖ Qualitative data collection method: semi-structured **exploratory interview**
- ❖ ... with twelve L1 sign linguists worldwide via an online platform (Zoom)
- ❖ Content
- ❖ The duration of the interviews is approximately 60 minutes.

Research methodology II: Data analysis

- ❖ Deductive content analysis
- ❖ Pre-defined categories based on the literature review
- ❖ Interview transcription
- ❖ Coding process in MAXQDA (categorization)

Overview of main issues

- ❖ Conceptualization of sign languages' grammar description
- ❖ Data collection
- ❖ Data analysis
- ❖ Presentation of sign language grammars

Conceptualization of grammar description

*„As I said, I'm a bit professionally unsure because the basics of grammar is always already based on the written form. In principle, the definitions are already in written form. But if the question, what is the grammar of sign language, I best leave the answer open. Because I have never seen a grammar appear completely in sign language without written form.“
(GR_001)*

Conceptualization of grammar description

„I think it is important that grammar should be described in sign language. Because sign language explains itself as its own system! Described it in other languages are always... different. Somewhat, they can never reflect sign language [as a system with the same depth.]“ (GR_003)

Data source

Signs from the lexicon only become understandable in the context of the grammar. I have often observed that the example sentences from the collection of [sign language name] explain certain signs from the lexicon, but these sentences are often not really naturally sign language. ... That's why I point to grammar, because it really arises in context and from that I can assign appropriate evidence for lexicon.” (GR_pr_002)

Data source

„It is important that linguists work from the corpus that [institution] has created. That would be ok.“ (GR_003)

Linguist's role (to the sign language communities)

„Because then the grammar can be shown and everyone can interpret it from their own perspective. I can ask them what they think about it. Do they see it the same way, or do they think differently? This gives me the opportunity to have more discussions with them about it, and I can add more. Without this grammar, I am alone; explaining it to them is not enough.“
(GR_002)

Presentation of sign language grammar

„I think that the material should be multimodal: it should have sign language versions, pictures within pictures, subtitles, and so on, which are informative.“ (GR_002)

But what is the next?

Emerging grammar description practice: Estonia

Estonian Sign Language Research Lab

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Background

- ❖ First phase in the development of Estonian Sign Language's grammar sketch
- ❖ Co-creation process between outsider L1 linguists as well as L1 and L2 Estonian signers who are researchers, too

First phase of investigation

- ❖ Designing the research with junior researchers
- ❖ Initiating literature review on Estonian Sign Language
- ❖ Workshop on sign linguistics: phonology and morphology with focus on the theoretical frameworks and the terminology

Perspectives in Grammar Description of Sign Languages

<p>II</p> <p>samaaegne liitsõna</p>	<p>Viibe, kus kaks komponenti esitatakse samal ajal, moodustades sellega uue tähenduse</p>
<p>n</p> <p>kindlaks määratud ühendid</p> <p>kokkusulandsõnad</p>	<p>Kahte või enamat märki kombineerides antakse konkreetne tähendus antud märgile.</p>

SAA → "G" HF
 EI SAA → "A" HF
 INVITE "ZERO"
 ↳ def with group & not invited
 INVITE EI-SAA → cannot!
 NEU RATAST POLE
 KAKS AKENT "A" → (only one window)
 KAKS AKENT ZERO → (no window)
 KAKS AKENT POLE, KAKS AKENT SIKER AKENT
 TAPU NEU ON
 ↳ existance
 NI HILJAKS → (no more)
 MITTE POLE
 ↳ "new" independent phrase
 TEGUSOOL POLE
 ZERO → omut miksistal
 MITTE

Agreement
 JARI → DAAKLEIT ISA → ARDM
 Jon: I GIVE BOOK FATHER X
 I FATHER BOOK GIVE
 I GIVE BOOK (exhaustive) → see book
 I GIVE BOOK (exhaustive) → more book
 ISA INVE HIND ZERO
 Jon: KEITI INVITE US AT
 Jon: ISA HINDA MEELDIMA
 - from agreement marker (PAM)
 ↳ first person
 ↳ non-first person
 M-ISA INVITE IX-VELDA
 INVITE EI-INVITE
 IX₁ IX₂₋₄
 INVITE ZERO → not invited in past
 INVITE ZERO → here is the person that did not invite her/him
 INVITE VEE → planned to invite later

Estonian expressions for „simultaneous compound“

Challenges

- ❖ Documentation of cross-linguistic variations
- ❖ Linguistic items that have not been documented to date
- ❖ Not just focusing on using check-list

Emerging community-based practice: Estonia II. – Next steps

- ❖ Verification process:
 - ❖ focus group meetings with sign language users
 - ❖ consultative meetings with sign language professionals and linguists
- ❖ Verification of the signed and written version in both way:
 - ❖ signed version verifies the written version
 - ❖ the written version verifies the signed version

Discussion I.

- ❖ Correspondence between the preliminary findings and the applied practices in Estonia
- ❖ Context:
 - ❖ language endangerment of undocumented sign languages (cf. Braithwaite, 2019)
 - ❖ linguistic diversity
 - ❖ community-based approach (Rice, 2018)

Discussion II.

- ❖ Different methodological approaches:
 - ❖ corpus-based methods
 - ❖ documentation-based methods
 - ❖ elicitation methods
 - ❖ check-list methods

Summary

- ❖ Mutually engagement (Bartha, 2016), co-creation framework
- ❖ Collaborative process with stakeholders and sign language communities (Ardavan, 2022)
- ❖ Involvement and control in the different phases of research projects (Yamada 2007)
- ❖ Capacity-building of deaf linguists
- ❖ Platforms and practices for knowledge production in collaborative work

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Thank you

References

Bartha, C. (2016). *Általános Nyelvészeti Tanulmányok XXVIII.* (C. Bartha, Ed.). Budapest: Akadémiai Kiadó.

Berez-Kroeker, A. L., Gawne, L., Kung, S. S., Kelly, B. F., Heston, T., Holton, G., Pulsifer, P., Beaver, D. I., Chelliah, S., Dubinsky, S., Meier, R. P., Thieberger, N., Rice, K., & Woodbury, A. C. (2018). Reproducible research in linguistics: A position statement on data citation and attribution in our field. *Linguistics*, 56(1), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1515/ling-2017-0032>

Desai, A., De Meulder, M., Hochgesang, J. A., Kocab, A., & Lu, A. X. (2024). Systemic Biases in Sign Language AI Research: A Deaf-Led Call to Reevaluate Research Agendas. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2403.02563*.

Dixon, R. M. W. (2010). *Basic Linguistic Theory. Volume 1: Methodology.* Oxford University Press.

Fenlon, J., & Hochgesang, J. A. (2022). Introduction to Signed Language Corpora. In J. Fenlon & J. A. Hochgesang (Eds.), *Signed Language Corporas* (pp. 1-17). Gallaudet University Press.

Guity, A. (2022). *Esharani Grammatical Sketch: An Initial Description of the Lexicon and Grammar* [Gallaudet University]. Washington D.C.

Hochgesang, J. A. (2022). Managing Sign Language Acquisition Video Data: A Personal Journey in the Organization and Representation of Signed Data. In A. L. Berez-Kroeker, B. McDonnell, E. Koller, & L. B. Collister (Eds.), *The Open Handbook of Linguistic Data Management* (pp. 367-383). MIT Press. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/12200.003.0035>

References

Holton, Gary, Wesley Y. Leonard, and Peter L. Pulsifer. 2021. People, ethics, and data. Open Handbook of Linguistic Data Management, ed. by Andrea Berez-Kroeker, Bradley McDonnell, Eve Koller, and Lauren Collister. Cambridge: MIT Press. http://gmholton.github.io/files/581-92248_ch04_1P.pdf

Leonard, W. Y., & Haynes, E. (2010). Making „collaboration“ collaborative: An examination of perspectives that frame linguistic research. *Language Documentation & Conservation*, 4, 268-293.

Mithun, M. (2014). The data and the examples: Comprehensiveness, accuracy, and sensitivity. In Nakayama, Toshihide & Rice, Keren (Eds.), *The Art and Practice of Grammar Writing* (pp. 25–52). University of Hawai'i Press.

Mosel, U. (2006). Grammaticography: The art and craft of writing grammars. In F. K. Ameka, A. Dench, & N. Evans (Eds.), *Catching Languages* (pp. 41-68). De Gruyter Mouton. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110197693.41>

Palfreyman, N. (2022). Managing Sign Language Data from Fieldwork. In A. L. Berez-Kroeker, B. McDonnell, E. Koller, & L. B. Collister (Eds.), *The Open Handbook of Linguistic Data Management* (pp. 267-276). MIT Press. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/12200.003.0026>

Rice, K. (2018). Collaborative research: Visions and realities. In T. B. Shannon & J. Carmen (Eds.), *Insights from Practices in Community-Based Research* (pp. 13-37). De Gruyter Mouton. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1515/9783110527018-002>

Yamada, R.-M. (2007). Collaborative Linguistic Fieldwork: Practical Application of the Empowerment Model. *Language Documentation & Conservation*, 1(2), 257-282.